

Touched by vibrations: Intensity modulates valence and arousal on the torso

Nedim Goktepe, Müge Cavdan, & Knut Drawing

Abstract — Previous studies have successfully elicited a wide range of emotional responses by stimulating the hand region. The purpose of the current study was to test whether tactile stimuli applied to the torso could elicit similar emotional responses. To this end, we created 45 custom vibrotactile patterns that were presented through a vibrotactile vest to the front, back, and both sides of the torso. The patterns covered a wide range of physical variables such as amplitude, trajectory, and continuity. In an exploratory experiment, participants rated the arousal and valence of these patterns. Emotional responses differed between the patterns, and detailed analyses suggested that vibration intensity and where these vibrations were applied influenced both valence and arousal judgments. In a follow-up experiment, we systematically varied the amplitude and location of the vibrations. Our results showed that lower amplitudes were less arousing and more pleasant than higher amplitudes. Similarly, vibrations to the back torso were less arousing and more pleasant than those applied to the front or both sides of the torso, which can be explained by the lower sensitivity on the back. Taken together, we suggest that perceived intensity partially explains the relationship between the emotionality of vibration patterns on the torso.

Index Terms— Emotion, Touch, Vibration, Torso, Valence, Arousal, Amplitude.¹

I. INTRODUCTION

In daily life, we touch surfaces and manipulate objects made out of different materials. Our interactions with these objects are modulated by their physical properties. Different materials and properties could also elicit different emotional responses [1]. For instance, satin feels more pleasant to touch than a bristle [2]. Our emotional responses to materials depend both on physical material properties and how we touch or are touched by the material [3]. Today, there are multiple systems and platforms to enhance user experience with tactile stimulation [4-7]. They offer a whole range of experiences and modes of interacting with real or virtual objects as well as with people. Naturally, emotion is a fundamental part of these modes of social and other types of interactions. Applied studies show that different emotions, say those generated in conversation, can be conveyed through tactile cues e.g., [8]. Similarly, text messages devoid of much visual and auditory information can

often lack emotional and social cues that are normally conveyed by the other person's visual or auditory appearance. This underlines the importance of conveying emotion from sensory channels other than vision or audition, such as touch.

Due to the rapid growth and adoption of these applications, there is a need to better understand the mapping between tactile properties and emotions. In emotion research, Russel's circumplex model [9] is often utilized, which describes emotion in two dimensions: valence and arousal. While valence describes the pleasantness or unpleasantness of an emotion, arousal describes its excitatory strength. Following this dichotomy, haptic research has been primarily focused on engineering haptic stimuli, mainly vibrations, to characterize the physical properties that elicit arousal and valence. For instance, Hasegawa et al. [10] used custom vibrations that vary in waveform, amplitude, frequency, duration, and duty ratio to study the role of these properties on the valence and arousal response of touch panel users. Similarly, Yoo et al. [11] also manipulated the amplitude, waveform, duration, and frequency of the vibrations delivered by a handheld smartphone. Both studies found an increased vibration amplitude delivered to the hand region is associated with high arousal and low valence (unpleasantness) [10-11].

Researchers often use standardized visual and auditory batteries to elicit emotional responses with a wide range of valence and arousal values. Perhaps, the most common of these batteries are the International Affective Picture System (IAPS, [12]) and International Affective Digitized Sounds (IADS, [13]), which provide standardized visual and auditory stimuli with various valence and arousal levels. Although the haptic domain lacks a well-established battery of stimuli, there are few candidates approaches that mainly focus on the hand region. For instance, Seifi et al. [14] developed a library of vibrations (VibViz) for a single actuator that evokes a range of arousal and valence, similar to emotional batteries of auditory (IADS [13]) and visual (IAPS [12]) stimuli. While the single actuator focus of the library is inviting many applications, it is established on the wrist region. However, haptic information is processed across the entire body and with considerable variation in sensitivity [15-16]. More importantly, emotional responses to touched materials

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This work involved human participants in its research. Approval of all ethical and experimental procedures and protocols was granted by the local ethics committee of University of Giessen under Application No. 2021-0034 and was in line with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013) except that the study was not pre-registered.

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vary depending on which part of the body is stimulated [17-19]. For instance, Essick et al. [17] showed that various fabrics feel more pleasant when stroked across the cheek than the inner arm. Thus, there is a knowledge gap on how emotions can be conveyed by tactile stimuli delivered to other body parts and whether the same physical properties are important. To fill this gap, in the current study, we focused on the torso region for eliciting emotions. The torso represents a large portion of the body, it is heavily involved in social touch [20] and contributes to emotional experiences. For instance, a previous study using a custom platform to deliver vibrations to torso found that vibrations to the upper torso enhance the fear and excitement of video clips [21].

The emerging wearable technologies, mainly haptic vests, scaffold research pertaining tactile stimulation of the torso by providing easy-access, standardized platforms, and replicable results across the globe. In the present study, we used such haptic vest to investigate a) whether it is possible to elicit feelings ranging in arousal and valence by delivering vibration patterns to the torso and b) whether these emotional responses can be traced back to the physical properties of the patterns. For the hand region, previous studies have identified different tactile properties modulating emotional response such as altering stroking speed [2] or direction [22], frequency, and amplitude [11], [14], [23-24]. Following the previous results, we first created a wide range of vibrotactile patterns varying in amplitude, trajectory, and number of active actuators to explore the design space. We additionally varied where these patterns were applied on the torso since the perceived intensity of vibration is different between the front and back of the torso [16] and other anisotropies have been reported [25-27]. The first experiment served as an exploration of the stimulus space suggesting effects of vibration location and amplitude on arousal and valence. We conducted a follow-up experiment, where we systematically varied the amplitude and location of different vibrotactile patterns to investigate their influence on valence and arousal.

II. METHODS

A. Participants

30 participants (23 females, mean age = 24.7 ± 3.7) completed the first part of the study. Another 30 participants (26 females, mean age = 24.7 ± 4.0) were recruited for the follow-up experiment. None of the participants reported any sensory impairment that would prevent them from performing their respective tasks in the experiments. All participants were compensated 8€/hour or with course credits for their participation. The study was approved by the local ethics committee LEK FB 06 with approval number 2023-0006 (Series 1) in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki [28] without preregistration.

B. Stimulus and Apparatus

A commercially available vibrotactile vest (TactSuit X40, bHaptics Inc.) was used to deliver vibration patterns in both experiments. The vest delivers between 90 -100 Hz vibration to the torso from its 40 eccentric rotating mass actuators with variable power (approximately 8.86-24.06 m/s^2) and has been used in previous research [16].

Fig. 1. Illustration of actuator placement on the front torso (left panel) and vibration patterns in Experiment 2 (right panel). Upper Panel: Please note that the placement of actuators could slightly vary between individuals based on their body type. Lower Panel: Patterns are depicted on one side of the torso. These were applied to the front, back, or both sides of the torso. Black arrows indicate the order and direction of activation of actuators.

Following previous studies [11], [14], [23-24], we explored the design space by creating 45 unique vibration patterns for Experiment 1 using the companion software of the vibrotactile vest. These patterns varied in mean amplitude as measured with an accelerometer (16.06 – 24.06 m/s^2), trajectory, motion pattern, continuity, and number of actuators, where they are applied on the torso. The vibrotactile patterns were designed to generate a continuous sensation of motion for the entire duration of the pattern (e.g., pattern #16 continuously simulated different parts of the torso, see Fig. 1). Thus, they allowed us to explore a wide range of physical characteristics (see Appendix 1 for a description of patterns which are available at <https://shorturl.at/U0ww0>).

In the follow-up experiment, a subset of patterns from the first experiment were used. In order to isolate the effect of location and amplitude as much as possible, we selected three similar patterns with continuous motion trajectory and comparable speed. They stimulated a large area on the torso (see Fig. 1) and shared a similar original mean amplitude (Mean amplitudes: Pattern # 2: 19.26 m/s^2 , Pattern # 16: 20.86 m/s^2 , Pattern # 36: 19.26 m/s^2). During Experiment 2, they were applied at their original amplitude, lower amplitude (17.66, 19.26, 17.66 m/s^2 , respectively), or higher amplitude (20.86, 22.46, 20.86 m/s^2 , respectively) to the back, front, or both sides of the torso.

In both experiments, a custom MATLAB (MathWorks Inc.) script was used with the Psychtoolbox [29] for controlling the experiment and collecting the responses.

C. Procedure

In the first experiment, after signing the informed consent, participants wore the vest in a stand-up position in front of the experiment computer. To diminish the impact of individual

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bodily features and characteristics on the actuator placement and contact area, the experimenter asked participants to maintain a straight posture while ensured the good fit of the haptic vest with the provided adjusters. These measures improved the consistency of actuator placement for different body parts, but they do not guarantee an exact placement. However, given [16] showed poor localization performance on torso using the same vest, these small variations in actuator placement are unlikely to yield different perceptual outcomes for different body types. In each trial, one of the vibration patterns was delivered to the torso. Following the offset of the pattern, participants rated the valence or the arousal level of the pattern on a 7-point Likert-type scale. Namely, they indicated how pleasant (1: *very unpleasant*, 4: *neutral*, 7: *very pleasant*) and arousing (1: *not at all exciting*, 4: *exciting*, 7: *extremely exciting*) each vibration feels respectively. They rated each level once for each of the 45 patterns. The order of patterns and the arousal/valence rating were randomized for each participant. Participants completed the rating tasks in about 20 minutes.

Similarly in the follow-up experiment, participants wore the vest in a stand-up position after giving consent. Differently in the follow-up experiment, each pattern was repeated four times for each amplitude level and location in a fully randomized order. Participants rated the valence and arousal of patterns in the same trial in randomized order. In total, participants completed 108 trials in around 15 minutes.

Both experiments started with the oral and written instructions of the experiment. Each trial started with a screen message warning the participant of the forthcoming start of the vibration pattern. Following the vibration offset, participants rated the valence or arousal of the patterns using the same 7-point Likert-type scale using a keyboard like Experiment 1.

C. Data Analysis and Parameter Description

The purpose of Experiment 1 was to explore and identify potential parameters of vibrotactile patterns that elicit different valence and arousal levels. Past studies already identified vibration amplitude and duration as parameters modulating valence and arousal [11]. Here, we defined amplitude of each pattern as the mean amplitude of the activated actuators. We explored two additional parameters that are related to the perceived intensity of the patterns: number of distinct subsequences and overall intensity. We defined a distinct subsequence as continuous vibration motion trajectory unfolding throughout the pattern duration. Hence, the subsequences in each pattern had equal duration. For instance, pattern #2 has four distinct subsequences applied to the upper corner of the back and front torso (two per side) invoking a diagonal up and down motion sensation. Similarly, pattern #16 generates two distinct sequences of up and down motion travelling vertically across the central part of the front torso. Finally, pattern #36 consists of one subsequence because there is a continuous apparent motion (indicated by black arrows in Fig.1) generated by actuators on the front side of the torso (See Supplementary Materials for other patterns). Overall intensity is a parameter that describes the spatiotemporal intensity generated by patterns. It is calculated as a product of amplitude, duration, and number of distinct subsequences. It is meant to capture the total energy of the pattern.

For data analysis, we first normalized the arousal and valence ratings by performing a z-score transformation for each participant separately for arousal and valence ratings to mitigate any potential difference in rating scale and strategy across participants. This preserves the order and variation in the rating of patterns within participants but normalizes the ranges across participants. For all statistical tests we used Shapiro-Wilk for checking normality and applied Greenhouse-Geisser when the assumption of sphericity was violated. Holm-Bonferroni (paired samples) and Tukey corrections were applied to post-hoc tests for multiple comparisons.

III. RESULTS

A. Vibration Patterns to Torso Elicit Different Emotional Responses

To check whether vibration patterns delivered to the torso elicit emotional responses, we analyzed the arousal and valence ratings of the participants. The normalized ratings of valence and arousal were submitted to two separate one-way repeated-measures analyses of variance (ANOVA) with patterns as within factor. The ANOVAs provided the first evidence of the effect of vibration patterns applied to the torso on arousal, $F(44, 1350) = 2.754, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.087$ and valence ratings, $F(44, 1350) = 1.647, p = 0.005, \eta_p^2 = 0.054$ of individuals.

As the next step, we used the normalized ratings to estimate the valence and arousal of each pattern (Fig. 2 lower panel) similar to well-established emotion stimulus batteries [12-13]. We found a significant relationship between the arousal and valence ratings of the vibration patterns, $r(44) = 0.516, p = 0.003$.

We explored which physical parameters, including location, amplitude, duration, number of distinct sequences within patterns and their three-way product influenced the valence and arousal ratings of the patterns. Since some of the patterns (13/45, see Supplementary 1) feature vibrations that vary in amplitude over time, we exclude them in the subsequent analyses.

We observed that the arousal and valence ratings of patterns were influenced by the location (which side of the torso they were applied, Fig. 2, lower panel) and amplitude of the patterns (Fig. 2). To test the effect of location on arousal and valence, we performed a one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) on average pattern ratings with location as a factor and arousal and valence as dependent variables. The MANOVA yielded a significant effect of location, $F(4, 60) = 9.288, p < 0.001, \text{ Pillai-Bartlett Trace} = 0.781$. The underlying one-way ANOVAs showed significant effects of location for arousal, $F(2,29) = 22.993, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.613$ and valence, $F(2, 29) = 4.4655, p = 0.018, \eta_p^2 = 0.243$. We followed this up with post-hoc tests separately for valence and arousal. For valence, vibrations to both sides of the torso were rated significantly more pleasant compared to vibrations to the front ($p < 0.013$). For arousal, vibrations to the back side of the torso were rated to be more arousing than vibrations to both ($p < 0.001$) or front side ($p < 0.001$) of torso.

Then, we analyzed the relationship between the number of distinct sequences in patterns with arousal and valence using correlational analyses. We reasoned that number of distinct patterns might play a role in the elicited arousal and valence as

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many sequences can be overwhelming or a few can be underwhelming.

Fig. 2. Valence and arousal ratings for each pattern (upper panel), sorted by torso location (lower panel). Upper panel: The orange line represents the best-fitting linear regression ($r^2 = 0.2195$). Lower panel: Mean arousal and valence rating on each location are presented by opaque points. Valence and arousal ratings for individual patterns are shown semi-transparent. Error bars show ± 2 standard errors.

To explore this possibility, we performed Spearman correlations between number of sequences with valence and arousal. We found no significant correlation for arousal ($\rho(30) = 0.011$, $p = 0.954$) but a positive significant correlation for valence ($\rho(30) = 0.452$, $p = 0.009$). Applying the same reasoning this time to the time domain, we checked whether the duration of patterns influenced the elicited arousal and valence. We did not find a significant correlation between duration and arousal ($\rho(30) = -0.191$, $p = 0.295$) or valence ($\rho(30) = 0.281$, $p = 0.119$).

Next, we checked if the amplitude of our patterns was related to valence and arousal. Accordingly, we performed Spearman correlations between mean pattern amplitude (16.06 to 24.06 m/s^2) and valence and arousal. There was no significant relationship between amplitude and valence ($\rho(30) = -0.118$, $p = 0.521$). We observed a positive relationship between amplitude and arousal but it did not reach significance ($\rho(30) = 0.292$, $p = 0.105$).

Finally, we checked the influence of overall intensity of patterns across time and space on valence and arousal. We defined

overall intensity as the product of the number of distinct patterns, their mean amplitude and duration. However, we found no relationship between overall intensity and arousal ($\rho(30)$

Fig. 3. The relationship of amplitude with arousal (up) and overall intensity (down) with valence.

$= 0.025$, $p = 0.891$). Yet, in contrast to amplitude, we found a significant correlation between overall intensity and valence ($\rho(30) = 0.575$, $p < 0.001$). The apparent disagreement between the overall intensity and amplitude can be explained by the amplitude range of the haptic vest we used. We observed that at the maximum amplitude the vest (24.086 m/s^2) was still producing relatively mild vibration, presumably a desirable design feature for an everyday commercial gaming product. This could also explain why patterns with higher intensities were perceived to be more pleasant. Furthermore, it is important to consider that these patterns vary in different dimensions for exploration of the stimulus space. Thus, the expected arousal and amplitude effect arises when all the spatiotemporal intensity parameters are combined.

B. Amplitude and Location of Vibrations to Torso Modulate Emotional Responses

In Experiment 1, we found an effect of location on the elicited emotional responses in line with previous studies suggesting variability of emotional responses on different body locations [17-18]. Like previous studies (e.g., [10-11]), we found a positive trend between amplitude and arousal. Considering the

goal of Experiment 1 was to explore the stimulus space, it included vibration patterns that are quite different from each other with respect to many variables in addition to amplitude and location. In order to directly test the effect of amplitude and location we conducted Experiment 2, where we manipulated a subset of the patterns in terms of their amplitude and which side of the torso they stimulate.

Fig. 4. Arousal and valence ratings in the experiment were sorted based on location (upper panel) and amplitude (lower panel). Mean arousal and valence ratings are shown by opaque points. Error bars show ± 2 standard errors.

As before, we ran a one-way MANOVA to test the effect of location on arousal and valence but this time to compare participant ratings instead of average pattern ratings. The MANOVA yielded a significant effect of location, $F(4, 116) = 43.584$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.601$. The underlying repeated-measures ANOVAs yielded significant effects of location on arousal, $F(1.36, 39.432) = 98.843$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.773$, and on valence, $F(1.514, 43.892) = 94.365$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.765$, after Greenhouse-Geisser correction. Post-hoc tests suggest that vibrations to the back of the torso were significantly less arousing but more pleasant than both to the front and to both sides of the torso (all $ps < 0.001$). Whereas vibrations to the front torso were

less arousing and less pleasant than the vibrations to both sides of the torso (all $ps < 0.001$, see Fig. 3). Next, we tested whether the vibration amplitude systematically modulated the arousal and valence ratings. Experiment 1 showed that overall intensity but not amplitude was positively correlated with valence.

While this can be attributed to other variables such as duration, in Experiment 2 we kept these variables constant and vary the amplitude of each pattern. This allowed us to compare the effect of amplitude on arousal and valence ratings in isolation and systematically (Fig. 4 bottom). We observed that the patterns with lower amplitudes were associated with lower arousal and more pleasant valence ratings than patterns with higher amplitudes (Fig. 4 lower panel). A repeated measures MANOVA suggested a significant effect of amplitude on arousal and valence ratings, $F(4, 116) = 12.615$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.303$. The underlying repeated measures ANOVAs yielded a significant effect of amplitude on arousal, $F(2, 58) = 32.563$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.529$. Post-hoc tests suggested that high amplitude was more arousing than mid ($p = 0.002$), and low ($p < 0.001$) amplitude and mid amplitude was more arousing than low ($p < 0.001$) amplitude. Similarly, there was a main effect of amplitude on valence, $F(2, 58) = 9.24$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.242$. Post-hoc tests suggested that high and mid amplitude patterns were significantly rated more negative than low amplitude patterns ($p = 0.005$, $p < 0.001$, respectively) yet statistically comparable to each other ($p = 0.764$).

IV. DISCUSSION

Tactile information constitutes an essential part of our emotional experience by providing emotional cues for social interactions or setting our preferences toward materials and surfaces. Although tactile information is processed across the entire body, previous research mostly focused on single body parts, mainly the hand region, to study tactile cues of emotion. These studies have successfully elicited a wide range of emotional responses by stimulating the hand region with vibrations varying in amplitude, frequency [10-11], direction [22], and speed [2]). Experiment 1 explored the design space to investigate if vibrations applied to the torso could elicit emotional responses. Like the hand region, we found that vibration patterns applied to the torso also evoke various emotional responses. Experiment 1 also served as an exploration of the stimulus space where we used different vibrations varying in amplitude, direction, trajectory, and the torso location.

Our exploratory analysis hinted at the effects of location, amplitude, and overall intensity of the stimulation on valence and arousal. Also, it suggested possible interactions between physical factors that differentially modulate the elicited emotional responses. This was especially evident in the relationship of overall intensity (the combination of amplitude, number of sequences, and duration) with valence. Like previous studies [10-11], we observed a positive relationship between amplitude and arousal. However, this effect did not reach significance probably because amplitude co-varied with other stimulus parameters.

Motivated and cautioned by these exploratory results, we conducted Experiment 2 to systematically test the role of amplitude and location of the patterns. As hinted in Experiment 1, we found that both location and amplitude modulated valence

and arousal judgments. More specifically, vibrations applied to the front side of the torso elicited more arousing but less pleasant responses than those applied to the back side of the torso. Similarly, high amplitude vibrations elicited more arousing but less pleasant emotional responses. The systematic manipulation of location and amplitude in Experiment 2 isolated from other co-varying parameters underlines the importance of these parameters in inducing affective responses. Thus, in line with the previous findings [10-11], Experiment 2 provides direct evidence of the effect of amplitude and extends them to the torso.

The perceived intensity of the vibration patterns could be a unifying variable explaining the effects of amplitude and body location on emotional responses. The perceived intensity of a vibration can be defined as a function of the vibration amplitude and the sensitivity of the applied location. According to this idea, Experiment 2 manipulated the perceived intensity in two different ways: by increasing the intensity of stimulation and by applying the stimulation to different parts of the torso varying in sensitivity [16]. Thus, applying the vibrations to the front torso as opposed to the back has a similar effect on arousal and valence as reducing the amplitude. However, it is important to note that, in Experiment 2 location differences modulated arousal and valence more than amplitude differences (Fig. 3). Therefore, the contribution of sensitivity and amplitude might have different weightings in the resulting perceived intensity. Finally, the vibration frequency of patterns might influence the perceived intensity. Frequency has shown to influence valence and arousal for vibrations from 60 to 300 Hz delivered to finger. Our patterns were approximately 90 Hz with negligible variance (see Supplementary Materials). Thus, future studies could investigate the frequency modulation of valence and arousal in the torso region.

In addition to sensitivity differences across body parts, emotional responses might be related to the strong emotional conductivity of tactile stimuli as a medium of conveying emotion in daily life as social touch and gesture [20], [30-31]. For instance, body parts that are more involved in expressing or receiving emotions (e.g., upper back) might be more susceptible to emotional modulation. Nevertheless, it is unclear whether the strength of the elicited emotional response varies with the social relevance of the stimulated body area. Moreover, considering the differences in sensitivity [15-16] and emotional responses across body parts [17-18], different sets of stimuli might be necessary for eliciting similar emotional responses in different body parts. A calming vibration for one body part can be alerting when applied to a more sensitive part of the body. In Experiment 2, we observed that the same vibration to different torso locations modulated the valence and arousal. However, it is unclear whether this effect is due to the sensitivity difference between the front and back of the torso or their social relevance. Future studies could test the role of social relevance by controlling the vibration sensitivity in different body parts. Relatedly, there could be sex differences sensitivity differences especially in the torso region. Our sample is not adequate for providing reliable statistical evidence as both of our experiments consisted of biological female participants in great majority (23/30 and 26/30, respectively). Yet, none of our female participants reported heightened sensitivity in the breast region in our surveys in both piloting stage and after the experiments.

Considering the use of tactile cues in various applications particularly vibrations on smartphones, touch panels, and haptic vests – understanding how different tactile stimuli elicit different emotions and sensations bears practical importance. Crucially, due to vibrotaction differences between individuals [15], the range of physical parameters for eliciting emotional responses might vary between individuals. Therefore, applications using tactile cues to induce different emotions (e.g., [5], [32-33]) should explore how different users respond to the tactile stimulation on different body parts. Furthermore, various products and technologies use vibrations to elicit a range of different complex emotions (e.g., excitement) and ambiances (e.g., football matches) in the context of gaming or other types of entertainment [28-29]. While stimuli for these applications are often tailored for specific scenarios, whether these stimuli can be effectively used for stimulating different body parts remains an open question. Our study contributes to this endeavor by providing a library of patterns with arousal and valence measurements that can be replicated or modified across the globe using the same commercially available haptic vest. However, it is important to note that our vest uses eccentric rotating mass actuators (ERMs). While ERMs are affordable and widely used in scientific and commercial applications [34], the amplitude and frequency of their vibrations are not separately controllable. Thus, it is worth noting that the amplitude modulation of patterns leads to negligible changes in vibration frequency (Supplementary Fig. 1).

V. CONCLUSION

We show that stimulating the torso with vibrotactile patterns elicits different emotions varying in arousal and valence. Particularly, in our explorative experiment, we found that the pattern location on torso and overall intensity of patterns influenced arousal valence of patterns. In a follow-up experiment, we pinned down these two important variables and confirmed their influence on valence and arousal. More specifically, we found that vibrations to the back of the torso are less arousing but more pleasant than to the front or both sides of the torso. Moreover, we extended the previous studies on the hand region to the torso by showing that amplitude directly modulates emotional responses in a way similar to stimulating different parts of the torso. We argue that the perceived sensitivity of vibrations, which is a function of the sensitivity of the body part and stimulation intensity, explains the emotional responses elicited by vibrations.

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Supplementary Materials

To explore the parameter space for eliciting emotional responses through vibrotactile patterns applied to torso, we created 45 patterns. These patterns primarily vary in which side of the torso they stimulate (location), amplitude (intensity), duration. Table 1 summarizes these parameters and corresponding arousal and valence ratings. Vibration patterns could also vary in their sequence as illustrated in Table 1. Illustrations were captured from bHaptics's free software: bHaptics Designer. The white empty circles are the location of the actuators. Active actuators are indicated with blue circles and pattern sequences with lines. It is important to note that when the pattern sequence lies between actuators, vibration stimulation is delivered by illusory vibrations, shown as lines in Table 1. These illusory vibrations are automatically created by the software [1] by activating the closest actuators at different amplitudes to elicit illusory vibrations akin to apparent haptic movement illusion [2]. The line length is proportional to the duration of each pattern and therefore reflects both the duration and trajectory of these sequences. Sequences that are serially linked and continuous are illustrated with connected lines. Parallel sequences are represented with separate circles and lines. The numbers within each circle represent the order, thus also the relative time of activation of each actuator. Active actuators in the same pattern stayed active for the same duration.

We measured the amplitude and frequency of the generated vibrations using a tri-axis accelerometer (ADXL345) with the following protocol. The accelerometer was firmly stuck to the encapsulation of the actuator while the vest was hanging perpendicularly to the floor. Then, output from the minimum to maximum amplitude of the vest (0-100%) was measured in 10 steps. Accelerometer data were acquired through an Arduino Uno from the orthogonal axis of the accelerometer for further calculations, since other axis were parallel to the vest and thus invariant to vibration. Then the data were then filtered offline using a 10 Hz Butterworth high-pass filter prior to amplitude calculations with the root mean square (RMS) method. The amplitude range of the actuator, measured in 10 steps, showed a linearly increasing profile. For this reason, we interpolated the intermediate amplitudes by fitting a linear function with an intercept. The mean amplitudes of patterns were calculated using this linear fit, which ranged from 16.09, to 24.09 m/s².

Supplementary Fig. 1. Amplitude-Frequency response curve of an actuator measured from the outside of the encapsulation.

Next, the amplitude-frequency dependency of the vest was measured. According to the manufacturer measurements, the nominal rotation speed of the actuators at maximum power is 7000 rpm (~120 Hz). In contrast, our measurements from the outside of the encapsulation show little to no variation in peak frequency following a fast Fourier transform (FFT). The measured frequencies do not exceed 100 Hz across the amplitude range of our patterns (Supplementary Fig. 1). We attribute this difference to the dampening from the encapsulation and the inclusion of ramp-up and -down of the actuators. As we are interested in perception, our protocol provides a better estimation of vibrations felt by participants as it accounts for the encapsulation.

Table 1. Description of patterns used in Experiment 1 with average arousal and valence normalized values. Primary pattern variables in the form of pattern location on the torso, amplitude, duration, and sequence are provided.

Pattern number	Arousal	Valence	Location (back, both, front)	Amplitude (m/s ²)	Distinct Sequences	Duration (ms)	Pattern Sequence
1	0.33	0.24	1	21.3659	3	940	
2	-0.03	0.18	2	19.2859	4	1000	
3	-0.44	0.03	3	20.8859	2	2000	
4 ¹	0.48	0.25	1	24.0859	2	1200	

5	0.57	0.55	2	24.0859	2	3000
6 ¹	-0.36	-0.08	3	19.2859	2	1000
7	0.38	-0.17	1	24.0859	1	1000
8 ¹	-0.45	-0.18	2	16.0859	4	2000

9	-0.17	-0.33	3	22.4859	2	1000
10	0.16	-0.12	1	24.0859	2	930
11	-0.1	0.07	2	20.8859	2	1500
12	-0.28	-0.30	3	20.8859	1	2000

13	0.14	0.18	1	20.8859	1	1000
14	0.22	0.10	2	19.2859	4	400
15	-0.12	-0.11	3	22.4859	2	1000
16	0.51	0.14	1	20.8859	2	950

17 ²	0.07	0.14	2	22.4859	4	2000
18	-0.25	0.13	3	22.4859	2	1000
19	0.44	-0.26	1	22.4859	2	1000
20	0.11	0.43	2	20.8859	4	1700

21	-0.21	0.01	3	20.8859	4	1000
22	0.15	0.24	1	22.4859	2	2000
23 ³	0.10	0.04	2	20.8859	4	1500
24 ¹	-0.29	-0.46	3	20.8859	2	1000

25 ¹	0.46	-0.12	1	19.2859	1	1000
26 ¹	0.19	-0.19	2	19.2859	2	1600
27	-0.08	-0.11	3	20.8859	1	2500
28 ¹	-0.45	-0.47	1	16.0859	1	1000

29	0.07	0.07	2	16.0859	4	1500
30 ¹	-0.35	-0.44	3	20.8859	4	1000
31	0.10	-0.26	1	22.4859	1	950
32 ⁴	-0.43	-0.09	2	16.0859	8	1000

33 ¹	-0.25	0.15	3	16.0859	2	2000
34	0.5	0.45	1	24.0859	4	1000
35 ⁴	0.24	0.15	2	24.0859	8	1500
36	-0.03	0.10	3	19.2859	1	1800

37	0.51	-0.11	1	22.4859	1	930
38	0.42	0.25	2	19.2859	2	2000
39	-0.48	0.05	3	19.2859	3	1000
40	-0.02	-0.03	1	20.8859	2	1500

45	-0.46	0.08	3	22.4859	2	1000	
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1: Patterns with variable amplitude.

2: Same pattern is executed by the two middle columns on the back.

3: The same pattern is executed in two rows below on the back.

4: These patterns were excluded from the correlational analyses in Experiment 1 due to having substantially more distinct patterns than the rest of the patterns.

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